

Studies in the Rearrangement of Spiranes: Part IV: Synthesis of 1', 2', 3', 4'-Tetrahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1, 2'-naphthalene], its 7'-Methyl, 6', 7'-Dimethyl Derivatives and 1', 2', 3', 4' 5' 6', 7' 8'-Octahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane 1,2' anthracene] and their Rearrangement on Catalytic Dehydrogenation

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The desired spirohydrocarbons 1', 2', 3', 4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1, 2'-naphthalene] (I, $R_1 = R_2 = H$), its 7'-methyl-(I, $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = H$) and 6', 7'-dimethyl (I, $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) derivatives and 1', 2', 3', 4', 5', 6', 7', 8'-Octahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1, 2'-anthracene] (I, $R_1 = R_2 = C_6H_5$) have been synthesised in order to study the mode of fission of the substituted spirocyclopentane ring during catalytic dehydrogenation. When heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst, the aforesaid spiranes are found to undergo smooth rearrangement yielding 1-ethyl-2-methylphenanthrene, 1-ethyl-2, 6-dimethylphenanthrene, 1-ethyl-2, 6, 7-trimethylphenanthrene and 3-methyl-4-ethyl-1, 2-benz anthracene (V) respectively. The structures of the latter three hitherto unknown hydrocarbone have been confirmed by authentic syntheses. The spiranes have been prepared by the Friedel-Crafts condensation of the anhydride of 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentene-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid with benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and tetralin respectively by an extension of the method developed earlier.

IN our previous communications^{1,2}, we reported the synthesis of different spiranes starting from the anhydride of 2,3-dimethylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid and benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and tetralin. They all underwent smooth rearrangement on catalytic dehydrogenation by way of fission of cyclopentane ring away from the substituent followed by angular cyclisation and dehydrogenation yielding phenanthrene derivatives without any loss of carbon atoms. In order to see if the rearrangement is a general one and the ring fission takes place in an identical manner in all such spiranes with different substituents in the cyclopentane ring irrespective of the nature of substitution, the synthesis of 1',2',3',4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] and its different derivatives have been undertaken in the present work. On catalytic dehydrogenation, all such spiranes suffered ring fission in an identical manner away from the substitution giving substituted phenanthrene derivatives. A more obvious explanation that the homolytic fission of the cyclopentane ring takes place at high temperature with the formation of a free radical which finally undergoes angular cyclisation and dehydrogenation is untenable at least in these cases, as such a manner of fission is likely to produce the more stable tertiary free radical by fission of the cyclopentane ring adjacent to sub-

stitution and thereby produce 3,4-disubstituted phenanthrene derivatives rather than 1,2-disubstituted derivatives. All attempts at the isolation of the former from the products of dehydrogenation have been abortive. The observed specificity in the fission of the disubstituted cyclopentane ring may be due to retropinacol type of rearrangement that the spiranes undergo prior to final dehydrogenation. The preferred fission of the substituted cyclopentane ring away from the substitution may be due to less interference of the substituents in the transition state with the peri hydrogen of the naphthalene system as explained in the earlier communication¹.

The starting material, 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentanone was prepared from ethyl laevulinate and *n*-propyl magnesium bromide according to the procedure described for the preparation of trans-2,3-dimethylcyclopentanone^{1,3}. The ketone on condensation with ethylcyanoacetate gave ethyl 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentylidene cyanoacetate which after potassium cyanide addition and hydrolysis furnished 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (II).

The anhydride of 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (II) on condensation with benzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium

chloride gave 1-phenacyl-2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III; $R_1 = R_2 = H$) in 80% yield. The presence of the $-CO-CH_2-$ grouping in the keto-acid was proved by the formation of a pyrylium salt with salicylaldehyde in the presence of dry HCl. The keto-acid on catalytic reduction in Paar apparatus gave 1-(β -phenethyl) 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid. The butyric acid derivative was cyclised by PPA to 3',4'-dihydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'(1'-H)-naphthalone]

keto-acid could not be reduced by Clemmensen method but on catalytic reduction in a Paar apparatus gave an excellent yield of the butyric acid derivative which on PPA cyclisation gave 7'-methyl-3',4'-dihydrospiro[2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'(1'-H)-naphthalen]-1'-one (IV; $R_1 = CH_3$; $R_2 = H$) in 68% yield. The spiro-ketone did not form a 2,4-DNP derivative but showed a strong I.R. carbonyl absorption at 5.95μ and on reduction by the Clemmensen method afforded the desired spirane

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1'-one (IV; $R_1 = R_2 = H$) in 68% yield, which, as expected, did not form a ketonic derivative due to steric hindrance and furnished the spirane, 1',2',3',4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] (I; $R_1 = R_2 = H$) on Clemmensen reduction. This when heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst underwent smooth ring transformation without any loss of carbon atom in an analogous manner reported earlier¹ giving 1-ethyl-2-methyl-phenanthrene.

The synthesis of spirane (I; $R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = H$) was carried out in a similar manner from the anhydride of II and toluene. The $AlCl_3$ catalysed condensation gave a single keto-acid, in 90% yield, which was proved to be 1-(4-methyl-phenacyl)-2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III; $R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = H$) by the oxidation of the keto-acid with sodium hypobromite solution to *p*-toluic acid. The

(I; $R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = H$) which when heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst gave 1-ethyl-2,6-dimethyl-phenanthrene. The structure of this hitherto unknown hydrocarbon was confirmed by an unambiguous synthesis by an extension of the method due to Bardhan and Nasipuri⁴. The condensation of β -*p*-tolyl ethylbromide, with ethyl 4,6-dioxoheptane-1,5-dicarboxylate⁴ in the presence of sodium ethoxide gave ethyl α -(2-*p*-tolyl)-ethyl- β -oxopimelate (VI) in good yield. This on cyclodehydration with conc. H_2SO_4 and subsequent hydrolysis furnished γ -(7-methyl-2-carboxy-3,4-dihydro-1-naphthyl)-butyric acid (VII) in about 40% yield. The methyl ester of this butyric acid derivative on Dieckmann cyclisation followed by alkylation with CH_3I gave 1-keto-2-carbomethoxy-2,6-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydro-phenanthrene (VIII) in 82% yield, which on hydrolysis afforded 1-keto-2,6-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexa-

Hydrophenanthrene (IX; $R_1 = CH_3$, $R_2 = H$). The ketone was condensed with ethylmagnesium iodide and the resulting alcohol on simultaneous dehydration and dehydrogenation by heating with 10% Pd-C catalyst afforded 1-ethyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene.

The Friedel Craft's condensation of the anhydride of II with *o*-xylene in symmetrical tetrachloroethane medium yielded 1-(3,4-dimethylphenacyl) 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$). The keto-acid on reduction in a Paar apparatus gave the corresponding butyric acid derivative in excellent yield, which on PPA cyclisation afforded 6',7'-dimethyl-3',4'-dihydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-(1'H)-naphthalen]-1'-one. The mode of cyclisation was established by its oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate to pyromellitic acid. The spiro-ketone on Clemmensen reduction furnished the spirane (I; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) which on catalytic dehydrogenation yielded 1-ethyl-2,6,7-trimethyl phenanthrene, identified by comparison with an authentic specimen synthesised from the condensation reaction of 1-keto-2,6,7-trimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (IX; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) with C_2H_5 MgI followed by simultaneous dehydration and dehydrogenation by heating with 10% Pd-C catalyst.

The $AlCl_3$ catalysed condensation of the anhydride of II with tetralin in cold nitrobenzene solution led to the formation of a single keto-acid proved to be 1-(1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-6-naphthyl) methyl-2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III, $R_1 = R_2 = C_4H_9$). The keto-acid on hydrogenation in a Paar apparatus gave good yield of 1-[β (1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthyl-6) ethyl]2-ethyl-3-methyl-cyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid which showed U.V. absorption characteristic of a β -methyl tetralin. The butyric acid derivative on PPA cyclisation afforded the ketohydroanthracene derivative (IV; $R_1, R_2 = C_4H_9$) which on Clemmensen reduction gave 1',2',3',4',5',6',7',8'-octahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-anthracene] (I; $R_1, R_2 = C_4H_9$). The spirane underwent rearrangement on catalytic dehydrogenation in an analogous manner yielding 3'-methyl-4'-ethyl-1,2-benzanthracene (V), identified by comparison with an authentic specimen synthesised from the condensation reaction between 4'-keto-3'-methyl-1',2',3',4'-tetrahydro-1,2-benzanthracene (X) and ethylmagnesium iodide followed by dehydration and dehydrogenation by heating with Pd-C catalyst.

Experimental

All m.p.s. and b.p.s. are uncorrected. U.V. spectra were recorded in 95% ethanol in Unicam Spectrophotometer, model SP 500. I.R. Spectra were recorded in Unicam Spectrophotometer, model SP 200G. Petroleum ether used had b.p. 60°-80°.

2-Ethyl-3-methylcyclopentanone

γ -Methyl- γ -n-propylbutyrolactone (20 g), prepared by inverse Grignard reaction between *n*-propylmagnesium bromide and ethyl laevulinate (1 : 1) in

dry benzene at -5° to 0°, was cyclised by stirring with PPA (250 g.) at 120° for 3 hr. The dark red reaction mixture was then decomposed with ice and the organic matter was thoroughly extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract, after successive washing with water, 5% $NaHCO_3$ solution and water, was dried and distilled when 2-ethyl 3-methyl cyclopent-2-ene-1-one⁵ (14 g.) was obtained in 80% yield.

A solution of the foregoing cyclopentanone derivative (50 g) in ethanol (60 ml.) was submitted to the process of hydrogenation with 1.6 g. of 10% Pd-C catalyst, when the calculated amount of hydrogen was taken up in 16 hr. The solution on filtration and distillation gave 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentanone (45 g.) boiling at 175° (Found : C, 76.23; H, 10.86%. Calcd. for $C_9H_{14}O$: C, 76.18; H, 11.11%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 115° (Found : N, 18.37%. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{13}N_4O_4$: N, 18.30%). The semicarbazone, crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 197° (Found : N, 22.68%. Calc. for $C_9H_{17}N_3O$: N, 22.95%).

2-Ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (II) :

A solution containing 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentanone (20 g), ethylcyanacetate (22 g.), ammonium acetate (4g.), acetic acid (8 ml.) and dry benzene (60 ml.) was refluxed on oil bath at 130°-140° for 6 hr. and then at 140°-150° for 12 hr. The reaction mixture was diluted with cold water; extracted with benzene, washed with water and then distilled when unsaturated nitrile (30 g., 93%) was collected at 125°/0.8 mm. n^{20}_D 1.4825. (Found : C, 70.42; H, 8.49%. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{19}NO_2$: C, 70.59; H, 8.59%);

A solution of potassium cyanide (18 g.) in water (36 ml.) was added to the foregoing unsaturated nitrile (25 g.) dissolved in rectified spirit (125 ml.). The solution was left for 10 days and then decomposed with dil. hydrochloric acid after removal of ethanol. The dicyanoester was extracted with benzene, washed with water and distilled when 19 g. (68%) of the dicyanoester was collected at 132°-133°/1.5 mm; n^{20}_D 1.4652.

The dicyanoester was then hydrolysed by heating under reflux with (1 : 2) hydrochloric acid (200 ml.) for 100 hr, when a solid mass separated out on cooling. The solid mass on purification by extraction with hot dil. sodium carbonate solution and subsequent acidification gave the desired acid (14 g.) which crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 156° (Found : C, 61.52; H, 8.34%. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{13}O_4$: C, 61.68; H, 8.41%).

The anilic acid, prepared by heating the anhydride of the above acid with aniline in benzene solution, was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 165° (Found : C, 70.51; H, 8.02%. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{23}NO_3$: C, 70.62; H, 7.96%).

1-Phenacyl-2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III, R₁ = R₂ = H)

A solution of the anhydride of II (9.8 g., 0.05 mole) in 15 ml. dry thiophen free benzene was added slowly to a well stirred solution of anhydrous AlCl₃ (14.68g., 0.11 mole) in 30 ml. of dry thiophen free benzene at -5° to 0°. The mixture after stirring at room temperature for 4 hr and then at 50°-60° for 1 hr. was decomposed with ice and HCl. After removing the excess benzene by steam distillation, the acidic matter was extracted with hot Na₂CO₃ solution, acidified and filtered. The residue on crystallisation from acetic acid and then from methanol gave the keto-acid (6.8 g) as plates, m.p. 123° (Found: C, 74.28; H, 8.21%. Calcd. for C₁₇H₂₂O₃: C, 74.45; H, 8.03%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallised from rectified spirit in shining yellow flakes, melts at 212°. (Found: N, 12.02%. Calc. for C₂₃H₂₆N₄O₆: N, 12.33%).

1-(β-Phenethyl) 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid

Five grams of the foregoing keto-acid (III; R₁ = R₂ = H) has hydrogenated in Paar apparatus as described earlier¹ to give the butyric acid derivative (4 g.) as colourless thick liquid which solidified on distillation and trituration with pet-ether. On repeated crystallisation from pet-ether it is obtained as colourless plates, m.p. 85°-86°. (Found: C, 78.66; H, 9.71%. Calc. for C₁₇H₂₄O₂: C, 78.46; H, 9.23%).

3',4'-Dihydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2' (1'H)-naphthalen]-1'-one (IV, R₁ = R₂ = H)

The foregoing butyric acid derivative (2.8 g) was cyclised¹ by stirring with PPA (30 g) on a steam bath for 1.5 hr when orange yellow colour was developed. Usual work up gave the spiro-ketone (IV; R₁ = R₂ = H) (1.8 g) as colourless liquid, b.p. 135°-140°/0.8 mm, n_D²⁵ 1.5490 (Found: C, 83.43; H, 8.82%. Calc. for C₁₇H₂₂O: C, 83.60; H, 9.01%).

It did not form the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative but showed a strong I.R. carbonyl absorption at 5.95μ and U.V. absorption at 229 mμ (log ε 4.4572), 249 mμ (log ε 3.8293) and 295 mμ (log ε 3.5892), characteristic of a conjugated cyclic ketone^{6(a)}.

1',2',3',4'-Tetrahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] (I, R₁ = R₂ = H)

The preceding spiroketone (1 g) was gently boiled under reflux with amalgamated zinc (20 g.), conc. hydrochloric acid (25 ml.), toluene (1 ml.) and acetic acid (1 ml.) for 80 hr. with the addition of conc. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) after every 10 hr. Usual work up followed by careful fractionation under reduced pressure afforded the spirane (I; R₁ = R₂ = H) (0.8 g.) as a colourless mobile liquid, b.p. 112°-115°/0.8 mm, n_D³⁰ 1.5429. (Found: C, 89.21%; H, 10.25%. Calc. for C₁₇H₂₄: C, 89.47; H, 10.53%).

Dehydrogenation of the spirane (I; R₁ = R₂ = H) with Pd-C Catalyst: Isolation of 1-ethyl-2-methylphenanthrene.

A mixture of the spirane (0.5 g.) and 10% Pd-C catalyst (60 mg.) was heated in a metal bath at 300°-330° for 3 hr. and then at 330°-350° for 1 hr. The mass was extracted with pet-ether, chromatographed over alumina and then sublimed under reduced pressure. The sublimate (0.25 g.) was converted into the picrate which crystallised from methanol in orange needles, m.p. 134° (Reported value⁷ for the m.p. of the picrate of 1-ethyl-2-methylphenanthrene is 134°-135°).

The hydrocarbon, 1-ethyl-2-methylphenanthrene, regenerated from the picrate in the usual way by passing its benzene solution through alumina followed by sublimation, crystallised from ethanol in colourless needles, m.p. 79°-80° (Reported value⁷ for the m.p. of 1-ethyl-2-methylphenanthrene is 80°). The *sym-trinitrobenzene complex* of the hydrocarbon, crystallised from ethanol in deep orange needles, melts at 153°-154° (Found: N, 9.67%. Calc. for C₂₃H₁₉N₃O₆: N, 9.70%).

1-(4-Methylphenacyl)-2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H).

The keto-acid was prepared starting from the anhydride of 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (9.8 g.) and toluene exactly by the same procedure as described for the preparation of (III; R₁ = R₂ = H) and on crystallisation from acetic acid gave 13.5 g. Keto-acid, m.p. 127° (Found: C, 74.82; H, 8.13%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₄O₃: C, 75.00; H, 8.33%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from ethanol in yellow plates, m.p. 206° (Found: N, 11.72%. Calc. for C₂₄H₂₈N₄O₆: N, 11.96%).

1-(β-4-Methylphenethyl) 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid

The foregoing keto-acid (6 g.) was reduced with hydrogen in a Paar apparatus according to the procedure described earlier¹. Usual work up followed by distillation under reduced pressure gave the reduced acid (5.5 g.) as colourless thick liquid which readily solidified on trituration with pet-ether. It crystallised from pet-ether in colourless compact plates, m.p. 123°-124° (Found: C, 78.65; H, 9.38%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₆O₂: C, 78.83; H, 9.49%).

7'-Methyl-3',4'-dihydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'(1'H)-naphthalen]-1'-one (IV; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H).

The foregoing butyric acid derivative (4 g.) was cyclised by stirring with PPA (60 g.) in an oil bath at 125° for 45 min when a deep colour developed. Usual work up followed by chromatography through alumina in pet-ether and distillation afforded the pure ketone (2.5 g.) as a colourless mobile liquid, b.p. 153°/2 mm, n_D³⁰ 1.5500 (Found: C, 84.18; H, 9.52%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₄O: C, 84.37; H, 9.37%).

The ketone did not respond to the usual tests for carbonyl group but showed a strong I.R. carbonyl absorption at 5.95μ and U.V. absorption max. at 233 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.1768); 251 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0536) and 296 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 3.3986), characteristics of a conjugated cyclic ketone^{6(a)}.

7'-Methyl-1',2',3',4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] (I; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H)

The above spiro-ketone was reduced by the Clemmensen method as described earlier. Usual work up and careful fractionation afforded the spirane (I; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H) (0.7 g.) as colourless mobile liquid, b.p. 138°–140°/0.6 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5420 (Found: C, 88.52; H, 10.30%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₆: C, 89.26; H, 10.74%).

Dehydrogenation of the spirane (I; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H) Isolation of 1-ethyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene.

A mixture of the spirane (0.4 g.) and 10% Pd-C catalyst (50 mg.) was heated in a metal bath at 300°–330° for 3 hr. and at 330°–350° for 1 hr. Usual work up and sublimation gave 0.2 g. of the hydrocarbon which was directly converted into picrate which crystallised from methanol as orange needles, m.p. 153°. It was identified as the picrate of 1-ethyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene by comparison with an authentic synthetic specimen.

The hydrocarbon, 1-ethyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene, regenerated from the picrate in the usual way, crystallised from ethanol in colourless fine needles, m.p. 88°–89°, not depressed on admixture with an authentic synthetic specimen.

Synthesis of 1-ethyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene: Ethyl- α -(2-p-Tolyl)-ethyl- β -oxopimelate (VI).

Ethyl 4,6-dioxoheptane-1,5-dicarbonylate⁴ (54.4 g.) was condensed with β -(*p*-tolyl)ethyl bromide (39.8 g.) b.p. 135°–137°/40 mm, prepared from β -(*p*-tolyl)ethyl-alcohol by the action of PBr₃ in benzene solution, in the presence of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (4.6 g.) and super dry ethanol (80 ml.), as described by Bardhan and Nasipuri⁴ to give the ketoester (28 g.) as a thick colourless liquid, b.p. 205°–207°/1.5 mm. It gives wine red colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

γ -(7-Methyl-2-carboxy-3,4-dihydro-1-naphthyl)-butyric acid (VII).

The foregoing keto-ester (VI) (10 g.) was slowly added with stirring to 50 ml. of conc. H₂SO₄ (d. 1.84) at –10° to –15°. The stirring was continued for 1.75 hr. at –10° when a deep blood red colour was developed. It was then decomposed with ice. Usual work up gave 5 g. of crude ethyl ester of γ -(7-methyl-2-carboxy-3,4-dihydro-1-naphthyl)-butyric acid which was directly hydrolysed by alcoholic KOH solution to give 4 g. of the crude acid which was purified by repeated crystallisation from acetic acid when the butyric acid derivative (3 g.) was obtained as short needles, m.p. 177°–178° (Found: C, 69.78; H, 6.28%. Calc. for C₁₆H₁₈O₄: C, 70.07; H, 6.56%).

The dimethyl ester of the acid (VII), prepared by the action of diazomethane on the ethereal solution was a thick oil, b.p. 190°–195°/0.7 mm. (Found: C, 71.28; H, 7.18%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₂O₄: C, 71.52; H, 7.28%).

2,6-Dimethyl-2-carbomethoxy-1-keto-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (VIII).

To a suspension of powdered sodium methoxide, prepared from 0.9 g. sodium, in 50 ml. dry benzene, the dimethyl ester of the acid (VII) (6.5 g.) was added. The mixture was then refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere on a steam bath for 3 hr. when a semisolid mass was obtained. To the cold solution of the sodio-derivative, 5 ml. of methyl iodide was added. The mixture was left overnight and then refluxed for 2 hr. Usual work up followed by distillation afforded 5 g. of the tricyclic ketone as a thick viscous liquid which solidified on trituration with pet-ether. After crystallisation from pet-ether it was obtained as fine flakes, m.p. 84°–85° (Found: C, 75.87; H, 7.21%. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₀O₃: C, 76.07; H, 7.04%). It showed U.V. absorption max at 241 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.16), 257 nm ($\log \epsilon$, r.13) and 300 nm ($\log \epsilon$, 4.15).

2,6-Dimethyl-1-keto-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene (IX; R₁ = CH₃; R₂ = H).

The foregoing keto-ester (VIII) (4.5 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with gl. acetic acid (90 ml.), conc. hydrochloric acid (45 ml.) and water (5 ml.) for 1.5 hr. under nitrogen atmosphere. Usual work up and distillation afforded 3.5 g. of a thick liquid which on chromatography over alumina in 1:1 benzene and pet-ether followed by crystallisation from pet-ether gave the pure ketone as colourless needles, m.p. 69°–70°. (Found: C, 84.57; H, 7.77%. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₈O: C, 84.95; H, 7.96%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and ethanol in red needles, m.p. 242°–243° (Found: N, 13.52%. Calc. for C₂₂H₂₂N₄O₄: N, 13.79%).

1-Ethyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene

A solution of the foregoing ketone (IX; R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H) (1 g.) in dry benzene (25 ml.) was added at room temperature to a well stirred solution of ethyl-magnesium iodide, prepared from magnesium (0.4 g.), ethyl iodide (5 ml.) and dry ether (30 ml.). The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr and then decomposed with ice and H₂SO₄. Usual work up and vacuum sublimation gave 0.8 g. of the semisolid mass which was heated with 0.1 g. of 10% Pd-C catalyst at 300°–320° for 1 hr. The mass was extracted with hot benzene and sublimed. The sublimate was converted into picrate which crystallised from methanol in fine orange needles, m.p. 153° (Found: N, 9.13%. Calc. for C₂₄H₂₁N₃O₇: N, 9.07%).

The hydrocarbon, 1-ethyl-2,6-dimethylphenanthrene, was regenerated from the picrate in the usual way and crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles, m.p. 88°–89° (Found: C, 92.16; H, 7.38%. Calc. for

$C_{18}H_{18}$: C, 92.31; H, 7.69%. It showed U.V. absorption maxima at 260 nm (log ϵ , 4.7254), 282 nm (log ϵ , 4.09), 292 nm (log ϵ , 3.9713), 304 nm (log ϵ , 4.0919), 322 nm (log ϵ , 2.4337), 338 nm (log ϵ , 2.6525), 347 nm (log ϵ , 2.1474) and 354 nm (log ϵ , 2.6148), characteristic of a substituted phenanthrene^(b).

The *sym*-trinitrobenzene complex of the above hydrocarbon crystallised from ethanol in orange yellow needles, m.p. 176°–177° (Found: N, 9.32%. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{24}N_3O_6$: N, 9.39%).

1-(3,4-Dimethylphenacyl)-2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III, $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$).

A mixture of the anhydride of II (4.9 g.) and 4 ml. of *o*-xylene was added slowly to a well stirred solution of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (7.43 g.) in *sym*-tetra chloroethane (25 ml) at 10°. The deep red complex formed after stirring at 10°–20° for 6 hr. and at 30° for 1 hr was decomposed with ice and HCl. Usual work up and crystallisation from acetic acid and then from ethanol gave the keto-acid (III; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) (5.3 g.) as colourless plates, m.p. 136°–137°. (Found: C, 75.04; H, 8.28%. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{26}O_3$: C, 75.49; H, 8.61%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, crystallised from ethanol in fine orange needles, m.p. 202°. (Found: N, 11.43%. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{30}N_4O_6$: N, 11.62%). Oxidation of the keto-acid (III; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) by sodium hypobromite solution gave, 3,4-dimethylbenzoic acid, m.p. 165°–166°.

1-(β -3,4-Dimethylphenethyl)-2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid.

The foregoing keto-acid (III; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) (4.5 g.) in 50 ml. ethanol was catalytically reduced with hydrogen in a Paar apparatus as described earlier¹ to give 4 g. of the reduced acid as thick liquid which solidified on cooling. It crystallised from pet-ether in colourless plates, m.p. 92°–93° (Found: C, 78.89; H, 9.68%. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{28}O_2$: C, 79.18; H, 9.72%).

6',7'-Dimethyl-3',4'-dihydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'(1'H)-naphthalene]-1-one (IV, $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$).

The foregoing reduced acid (3.5 g.) was cyclised as before by stirring with PPA (90 g.) on the steam bath for 1 hr. when the spiro-ketone (IV; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) (3 g.) was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 170°–172°/0.8 mm., n_D^{20} 1.5470. (Found: C, 84.21; H, 9.74%. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{26}O$: C, 84.44; H, 9.63%).

The ketone did not form the 2,4-D.N.P. derivative but it showed strong I.R. carbonyl absorption band at 5.95 μ and U.V. absorption max. at 235 nm (log ϵ , 3.621), 262 nm (log ϵ , 4.1452) and 300 nm (log ϵ , 3.4516), characteristic of a conjugated cyclic ketone^(a). Oxidation of the spiro-ketone with alkaline potassium permanganate solution⁸ gave pyromellitic acid, m.p. 280°.

6',7'-Dimethyl-1',2',3',4'-tetrahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-naphthalene] (I, $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$)

The foregoing spiro-ketone (1.2 g) was reduced by the Clemmensen method as described earlier¹ to

give the spirane (I; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) (0.9 g.) as a colourless mobile liquid, b.p. 155°–157°/0.6 mm. (Found: C, 88.20; H, 0.21%. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{28}$: C, 89.06; H, 10.94%)

Dehydrogenation of the spirane (I; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$): Isolation of 1-ethyl-2,6,7-trimethylphenanthrene.

The spirane (0.4 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (100 mg.) in a metal bath at 320°–330° for 3 hr. and at 330°–350° for 1 hr. usual work up followed by vacuum sublimation gave a thick mass which was converted into picrate in benzene solution. The separated picrate on crystallisation from benzene and methanol was obtained as orange needles, m.p. 155°–156°, not depressed on admixture with the picrate prepared from a synthetic specimen of 1-ethyl-2,6,7-trimethylphenanthrene.

The hydrocarbon, regenerated from the picrate, crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 135°–136° and was identified as 1-ethyl-2,6,7-trimethylphenanthrene by comparison with an authentic synthetic specimen.

Synthesis of 1-ethyl-2,6,7-trimethylphenanthrene

A solution of ethylmagnesium iodide, prepared from magnesium (0.2 g.), ethyl iodide (5 ml) and dry ether (30 ml), was added to a solution of 1-keto-2,6,7-trimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10-hexahydrophenanthrene* (IX; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) (0.5 g.) in dry benzene (15 ml) at room temperature. The mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. The cold solution was decomposed with cold 2(N) HCl. Usual work up and sublimation under reduced pressure gave 0.45 g. of a semi-solid mass which was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (50 mg.) in a metal bath at 300°–320° for ½ hr. Extraction with benzene followed by chromatography over alumina in pet-ether and sublimation gave the hydrocarbon as a solid mass, which crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 135°–136° (Found: C, 91.78; H, 7.82%. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{26}$: C, 91.93; H, 8.07%). It showed U.V. absorption max. at 354 nm (log ϵ , 2.8716), 337 nm (log ϵ , 2.9318), 322 nm (log ϵ , 2.9764), 304 nm (log ϵ , 4.2151), 291 nm (log ϵ , 4.1671), 283 nm (log ϵ , 4.2934) and 260 nm (log ϵ , 4.878), characteristic of a substituted phenanthrene^(b).

The picrate of 1-ethyl-2,6,7-trimethylphenanthrene crystallised from a mixture of benzene and ethanol in orange needles, m.p. 155°–156°. (Found: N, 8.63%. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{28}N_3O_7$: N, 8.80%).

The *sym*-trinitrobenzene complex of 1-ethyl-2,6,7-trimethylphenanthrene crystallised from ethanol in orange needles, m.p. 188°–189° (Found: N, 9.22%. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{28}N_3O_6$: N, 9.11%).

1-(1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-6-naphthoyl) methyl 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid (III; $R_1, R_2 = C_4H_9$).

The condensation of the anhydride of 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid (4.9 g.)

* It was prepared from 4- β -O-xylylethyl by an adaptation of the method of Bardhan and Nasipuri⁴ as described earlier.

with tetralin (3.3 g.) in presence of anhydrous AlCl_3 (7.33 g.) in nitrobenzene medium as described earlier gave the keto-acid (III; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$) (4 g.) as stout plates (acetic acid), m.p. 131° (Found : C, 76.68; H, 8.72%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_3$: C, 76.82; H, 8.53%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in orange yellow needles, m.p. $174^\circ\text{--}175^\circ$ (Found : N, 10.88%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$: N, 11.02%). Oxidation of the keto-acid with alkaline potassium permanganate solution gave trimellitic acid, m.p. 215° .

1- $[\beta$ -(1,2,3,4-Tetrahydronaphthyl-6) ethyl] 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1-carboxylic acid.

The preceding keto-acid (III; $R_1, R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$) (4 g.) was reduced with hydrogen in Paar apparatus according to the procedure described earlier¹. Usual work up followed by distillation gave the reduced acid (3.5 g.) as a thick liquid which solidified on trituration with pet-ether. It crystallised from pet-ether in plates, m.p. $102^\circ\text{--}103^\circ$. (Found : C, 79.84; H, 9.51%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2$: C, 80.25; H, 9.55%). Its U.V. absorption max. at 266 nm (log ϵ , 2.523), 270 nm (log ϵ , 2.702), 278 nm (log ϵ , 2.73), was characteristic of β -methyl tetralin^{6(c)}.

3',4',5',6',7',8'-Hexahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'(1'H)-anthracene]-1'-one (IV; $R_1, R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$).

The foregoing butyric acid derivative (3 g.) was cyclised by stirring with PPA (50 g.) on a steam bath for 45 min. when an orange red colour was developed. Decomposition with ice and usual work up followed by distillation under reduced pressure afforded the spiro-ketone (IV; $R_1, R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$) (2.2 g) as a colourless thick liquid; b.p. $210^\circ\text{--}215^\circ/0.7$ mm. (Found : C, 85.10; H, 9.42%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}$: C, 85.14; H, 9.46%). The ketone showed strong I.R. carbonyl absorption at 5.95μ and U.V. absorption max. at 263 nm (log ϵ , 3.9414) and 300 nm (log ϵ , 3.3681) characteristics of a conjugated cyclic ketone^{6(a)}, and on oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate solution gave pyromellitic acid, m.p. 280° .

1',2',3',4',5',6',7',8'-Octahydrospiro [2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentane-1,2'-anthracene] (I; $R_1, R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$).

The spiro-ketone (IV; $R_1, R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$) was reduced by the Clemmensen method as described earlier. Usual work up followed by careful fractionation under reduced pressure gave the spirane (I; $R_1, R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$) as a thick liquid, b.p. $185^\circ\text{--}187^\circ/0.7$ mm. (Found : C, 88.41; H, 9.92%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}$: C, 89.36; H, 10.64%).

Dehydrogenation of the spirane (I; $R_1, R_2 = \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$) : Isolation of 3'-methyl-4'-ethyl-1,2-benzanthracene (V).

The foregoing spirane (0.5 g.) was heated with 10% Pd-C catalyst (60 mg.) in a metal bath at $320^\circ\text{--}330^\circ$ for 3 hr. and then at $330^\circ\text{--}350^\circ$ for 1 hr. Usual work up followed by sublimation under reduced pressure gave the hydrocarbon as a yellow solid (0.1 g.) which crystallised from pet-ether in light yellow flakes, m.p. $175^\circ\text{--}176^\circ$. It was identified as 4'-ethyl-3'-methyl-1,2-benzanthracene (V) by comparison with an authentic synthetic specimen.

Synthesis of 3'-Methyl-4'-ethyl-1,2-benzanthracene (V)

To a solution of the grignard reagent, prepared from 0.2 g of Mg, 5 ml. of ethyl iodide and 30 ml. of dry ether was added a solution of 4'-keto-3'-methyl-1',2',3',4'-tetrahydro-1,2-benzanthracene* (X) (0.5 g.) in dry benzene (25 ml.), at room temperature. The solution was refluxed for 6 hr, cooled and decomposed with dil. sulphuric acid. Usual work up and distillation under reduced pressure gave 3'-methyl-4'-ethyl-1',2'-dihydro-1,2-benzanthracene (0.4 g.) as a yellow solid which crystallised from a mixture of benzene and pet-ether in light yellow flakes, m.p. $150^\circ\text{--}151^\circ$. 0.1 gram of this compound was heated with 50 mg. of 10% Pd-C catalyst in a metal bath at $330^\circ\text{--}320^\circ$ for 0.5 hr. Usual work up and sublimation under reduced pressure gave 50 mg. yellow solid which on crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and pet-ether yielded 3'-methyl-4'-ethyl-1,2-benzanthracene (V) as light yellow flakes, m.p. $175^\circ\text{--}176^\circ$ (Found : C, 93.21; H, 6.52%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}$: C, 93.33; H, 6.67%). It showed U.V. absorption max. at 230 nm (log ϵ , 4.5106), 245 nm (log ϵ , 4.3946), 255 nm (log ϵ , 4.3857), 274 nm (log ϵ , 4.4945), 285 nm (log ϵ , 4.8071), 296 nm (log ϵ , 4.8766), 318 nm (log ϵ , 3.7324), 332 nm (log ϵ , 3.8557), 346 nm (log ϵ , 3.8929), 364 nm (log ϵ , 3.7073) and 392 nm (log ϵ , 2.9263), characteristics of a substituted 1,2-benzanthracene.

The picrate prepared in benzene solution, crystallised from benzene in red cubic plates, m.p. $142^\circ\text{--}143^\circ$ (Found : N, 8.20%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_7$: N, 8.42%). The sym-trinitrobenzene complex crystallised from ethanol in orange needles, m.p. $162^\circ\text{--}163^\circ$ (Found : N, 8.52%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6$: N, 8.69%).

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* It was prepared from 4'-keto-1', 2', 3',4'-tetrahydro-1,2-benzanthracene² by glyoxalylolation followed by methylation and hydrolysis.